

Student -Faculty Academic &Outreach Performance Analysis System Using PHP & MySql

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Abstract:

I have made a project to analyze performance automatically as well as systematically instead of manually. The major reason for this project is to give encourage confidence and best career to a person by awarding him/her student/faculty of the year. This student & faculty performance analysis system provides an easy way to find the details of grade, rank & academic & other curricular activities performance report. because an individual institution should award a student as well as faculty as student/faculty of the year, by analyzing their performance. By this Students can get placed in good companies and faculty can get higher promotion. This is the project that helps an individual institution to manage its evaluation result. For that we have to find out marks, grade point of semester exam, attendance, discipline, respecting, cultural talent then sports and athlete performance of students and after analyzing all details we can award him/her student of the year. For any faculty we have to look his/her teaching skills, how he/she teaching to students how he can make understand to a weak student, how he/she make topper of his 99% student of his/her class how he/she maintaining relation with all students and other teaching and non-teaching staff, then we have to see his/her punctuality and discipline and it will be decided who deserve faculty of the year.

Keywords: php, mysql, data analysis, performance analysis